

Data management plan for the project "Social economy and farming resilience in Latvia"

Version 1

Description

The data management plan is developed in the framework of the project EU Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007), research grant project No. ESS2024/465-ZG-11 (project manager: Dr.sc.Soc. Aija Zobena 1st September 2024 – 28th February 2026, 65 534.00 EUR).

The main aim of the current research proposal is to study potential of social farming as a form of social economy in Latvia to mobilize collective action with self-help and autonomy, new communication technologies and social innovation in provision of social services and access to social infrastructure, in development of new social services and opportunities for social entrepreneurship. The contribution of social entrepreneurship to the resilience of territories also will be studied.

Keywords: social economy, rural development, cohesion policy, social farming, farming resilience

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

EU Recovery and Resilience

Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

Aija Zobena (0000-0003-4660-2886)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data management plan for the project "Social economy and farming resilience in Latvia"

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Organizations:

University of Latvia

Contact: Zobena Aija (aija.zobena@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: EU Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

3. License

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4. Templates

Descriptions

Transcripts of interviews

Considering the project aim and objectives, data collection and research methods will be organised according to an explanatory design. Literature studies will review Latvian regulatory measures, statistical data, and enclose a review of other national and international studies. The results of the literature review will be used to operationalise the framework for data collection and interpret results of the data analysis.

Case studies (5 to 7) of social entrepreneurship initiatives in all regions will be conducted to analyse social farming as form of social entrepreneurship in the context of social services provision as a response to challenges of shrinking society and uneven regional development. The focus will be on potential of social farms to provide social services in sparsely populated areas and potential role of LEADER and CLLD strategies in development of projects such as social farming.

Semi-structured interviews as a method will be carried out with national and foreign experts, and stakeholders. The analysis will employ thematic analysis, which can support design of research tools or interpret the results.

Focus groups are utilised to access small farmers to understand their motivation and interest in innovative forms of farming, particularly social farming. At least 5 focus groups will be carried out in different regions to reach participants across a variety of sociocultural and economic groups.

The web survey's aim is to gather quantitative data to capture the main trends of farming

strategies of small farms in Latvia.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

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1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Transcripts of FGD and interviews, farm survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

MS Word Document, SPSS Statistics Data Document

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Not applicable

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

for this project only

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

Not applicable

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Not applicable

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

Not applicable

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Not applicable

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Aija Zobena

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords

- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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